

WAYS OF EXPRESSING REQUESTIVE DIRECTIVE SPEECH ACTS: REQUESTS AND BEGGING

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12684168>

Abstract. The following thesis is focused on requestive type of directive speech acts and the ways of expressing them with the help of different lexical units. Moreover, the semantic and pragmatic features of requestive and begging speech acts are explained with examples.

Key words: directive speech acts, request, begging, implicit, explicit, addressee, addresser.

A request is a speech act belonging to the requestive type of directives, the purpose of which is to encourage the addressee to perform a certain action and at the same time to change the current situation. The fact that the performance of the action is not obligatory distinguishes the speech act of request from the act of command or instruction, and the aspect of "usefulness" of the action for the speaker distinguishes the act of request from the act of advice. For example, the illocution "Open the window" can be interpreted in 3 different ways: a) due to the fact that the air in the room is warm for the speaker, here the act of opening the window is useful for the addressee (please); b) when the speaker thinks it is right to open the window because he thinks it is necessary to change the air for the listener (advice); c) when the teacher enters the auditorium and says that it is necessary to open the window, taking into account the heat of the room, the execution of the action is not even discussed and is carried out without words (instruction).

The main feature of a request as a speech act is that the performance of the action is not mandatory, it is useful for the speaker, the desire of the addressee and the priority of his position. According to the way the speaker expresses his desire, it is divided into direct and indirect.

The indirect form of the speech act of request implies an implicit expression, the intention to perform an action or an urge to change the situation is realized in the hidden meaning of the speech act text. For example, expressing the ability or desire of the listener to perform a certain action using a question. A request is a speech act that is used in a dialogical form and is determined by communicative and pragmatic factors such as the intention of the speakers, their clear goal setting, and the ethnocultural factor.

A. Vejvinskaya, considering the request as one of the genres of speech act, offers the following semantic formulas to describe it:- I want you to do a good deed for me (X);-I say this because I want you to do it;-I don't know if you will do this because I know you are not obligated to make it a reality.

Thus, we recognize the following conditions for its successful implementation:

1. Predictability due to the fact that the speaker knows in advance that the listener will be able to perform the requested action;
2. The addresser forces the addressee to perform a certain action;
3. The existence of conditions such as the presence of certain reasons for the speaker to achieve the goal;
4. The producer fulfills a specific requirement for the recipient;
5. Communication participants should not be in a mutually hostile position.

It is necessary to take into account the national characteristics of speech act etiquette norms when mastering different forms of requests. Thus, the special forms of expressing a request in English are passive interrogatives and imperatives. Therefore, in the appropriate communicative situation Will you...? Can you...? it is advisable to replace it with a question form.

Direct request can also be expressed using performative verbs (ask, beg, etc.), but this method is very rare. Let's look at some examples with these verbs: "but do what I ask you first, and I ask you to give this message for God Almighty's sake." (Ch. Dickens, Oliver Twist)

The combination of the verb "let" with the infinitive is also used to express the tactics of direct motivation: "Why not let us get married in April and go abroad for the summer?" she asked once, after they had reached a silent understanding that marriage would eventually follow. (T. Dreiser, Jennie Gerhardt, p. 296). In this example, the girl is asking the guy to marry her and to go abroad next summer.

We also include the use of the verbs «look" or "come on" at the beginning or end of an expression as a means of softening the urge to direct action. Constructions of this type are found in the communication of people who know each other well, they stimulate communication and make statements more reliable. In many cases, such sentences are accompanied by modifiers or politeness, which make the communication friendlier, for example: Look, I'm really sorry about that telephone call. I hope the Muggles didn't give you a hard time. (J.K.Rowling, Harry Potter).

According to T.V.Larina, two types of requests can be distinguished among these types of statements:

1) object-oriented, that is, directed to the listener: Can you picture those clothes very clearly, Neville? Can you see them in your mind's eye? (J.K.Rowling, Harry Potter).

2) addressed to the speaker: "Can I just hold it Harry?" (J.K.Rowling, Harry Potter).

The use of the pronoun "we" shows the relationship of the speaker with the interlocutor in the communication and emphasizes that the addressee does not place himself above or below the interlocutor. In such cases, a special secret intonation appears, and the communication will not have a coercive character. This makes communication more comfortable and increases the speaker's chance of expecting a positive reaction from the listener:

Begging is a directive speech act and the distinctive feature of begging is the reluctance of the addressee to perform the action. The pragmatic presupposition of this speech act is that the speaker has a strong reason and tries to overcome the resistance of the listener, even if using various assertive methods.

According to N.I. Formanovskaya, "challenge is, on the one hand, the leading goals of the speaker expressing his will, and on the other hand, it is a prompt that leads the addressee to action." The classification of directive acts "attracts the attention" of researchers, first of all, according to the complexity of expressing one's opinion, and secondly, according to the fact that the intention to encourage action is diverse, such as command, demand, offer, request, begging.

In order to achieve his intention, the petition is made by a continuous request for the respect of the human rights that are dear to the speaker. According to N.I. Formanovskaya, the realization of a request is often expressed in an explicit form and is subjectively important, regardless of its objective value for the speaker.

In the speech act of prayer, the speaker often calls on the listener to feel sorry for him.

In English the following expressions are used to achieve the effect of the addressee's response:

a) the speaker begs the listener to fulfill his intention of friendship, fraternity, mutual respect, which is dear to the speaker:

It is expressed by means such as *"For the sake of", for goodness sake"*.

"Oh, for Heaven's sake!" Hermione cried. "Listen to me all of you"(R.K. Rowling, Harry Potter).

"Come along, for goodness sake," replied Lester. "I hope you do.... I'll see you tomorrow before we leave."(T. Dreiser, Jennie Gerhardt).

3) with the help of performative verbs such as "kneel", "cry":

"Let me say a prayer." Do! Let me say one prayer. Say only one, upon your knees, with me, and we will talk till morning."(Ch. Dickens, Oliver Twist)

The request directive act is characterized by the fact that the speaker does not give the listener an opportunity to think about the requested action during the communication, the request is not planned, it is expressed in an unexpected situation. As a result, the addressee is forced to give an immediate response, in other words, to react immediately to the requested action.

In the requisitive act of speaking, Paul Grice's Maxim of "quantity" is violated: the speaker's speech is more than sufficient, longer than the accepted norm. Compared to a request, begging is enriched with strategies of persuasion and entreaty of the communicator. In a request, the speaker addresses the interlocutor, putting the sense of self-respect last, based on the situation. The main reason for this is that the petitioner is forced to ask more than necessary because he realizes that it is difficult to fulfill his wishes with a request or an order.

The sentences we discussed above make the request directive act clearer, create the basis for its implementation, and invite some consideration before the recipient refuses to comply with the stated request. Thus, the act of request has a stronger emotional impact than the directives of the request, which means that the author agrees to any condition for its fulfillment.

In summary, the requestive directive speech acts are divided into two, the request act is when the speaker asks the listener to perform a certain action, while begging is when the addresser pleads with the addressee for the realization of the desired intention and agrees to any conditions for the accomplishment of the action.

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